

AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF A DYSFUNCTION OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINT IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract – In the structure of dental diseases, dentoalveolar anomalies (DVA) take the third place in frequency and prevalence after dental caries and periodontal diseases [10,15], in addition, in the last 30–40 years, a tendency to increase the frequency of DVA in children has been observed, this is due to the fact that in their formation, stable pathological mechanisms operate [2,11,19,20], in the place of those very important factors for the development of DVA and deformities, including pathology of the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) of a person, there has been a reduction in DVA that has been going on for many millennia and ongoing now [6].

Key words: dentoalveolar anomalies, temporomandibular joint, pathological mechanisms operate, dental caries, periodontal diseases.

I. Introduction

The growth of the cerebral part of the skull and the upright posture led to a decrease in the facial part of the skull, a decrease in the jaws, a change in their size, shape, morphology, and even etiopathogenetic formations of the organ pathology in the area of the emergency. Recently, diseases of the TMJ and chewing muscles are very common and are diagnosed in 20-80 % of dental patients. However, such patients with pain in the chewing muscles of the TMJ and seek medical help from a neurologist or therapist, not a dentist. The prevalence of this pathology is affected by conditions and lifestyle, the age of patients, the state of their chewing apparatus and a number of other factors [6,7,8,17,18]. Along with this, the incidence, diagnosis and treatment of pathology of the TMJ and chewing muscles in adolescents and adults have been little studied, and the available information on the frequency of this pathology is contradictory.

The aim of the study was a comprehensive approach to the diagnosis of TMJ pathology in children and adolescents, as well as to develop ways to correct them.

II. Literature review

Materials and methods of the research: To solve the tasks in the diagnosis of pathology in the TMJ among children and adolescents, 300 patients were examined, including 145 patients with DVA and deformations of students in secondary schools who were undergoing medical examination and turned to a specialist dentist at the Department of Orthopedic Dentistry »BukhMI and regional children's and adult dental clinic in Bukhara.

During the research, all ethical principles were observed, and also, given the complexity of the clinical course and diagnosis of the TMJ pathology, the diagnostic process was divided into two stages; at the first, information obtained directly from the patient was collected and analyzed, and his subjective opinion was heard about what began and how the disease developed; and at the second stage, objective symptoms were established, a detailed examination of the patient was carried out. In order to increase the diagnostic efficiency, we developed a unified coding map of the clinical examination, which includes a list of signs of non-inflammatory TMJ pathology.

III. Analysis

During the research, all ethical principles were observed, and also, given the complexity of the clinical course and diagnosis of the TMJ pathology, the diagnostic process was divided into two stages; at the first, information obtained directly from the patient was collected and analyzed, and his subjective opinion was heard about what began and how the disease developed; and at the second stage, objective symptoms were established, a detailed examination of the patient was carried out. In order to increase the diagnostic efficiency, we developed a unified coding map of the clinical examination, which includes a list of signs of non-inflammatory TMJ pathology.

To assess the morphometric parameters of the DVA (teeth, jaws, face, head, face), anamnestic medical and sociological data, 300 young men aged 6 to 18 years living in the city of Bukhara were studied; of which 130 boys (43.33%) and 170 girls (56.66); and also, out of them, 145 children and young people with TMJ pathologies (the main group - MG) and 155 - absolutely without TMJ pathologies (the control group - CG) (table No. 1).

Table №1.

By gender and age group, children examined, n = 300

Age quantity		Total		Girls		Boys	
		quantity	in %	quantity	in %	quantity	in %
6-9 years old 67/22,33%	MG	25	8,33%	13	4,33%	12	4,06%
	CG	42	14%	22	7,33%	20	6,66%
10-13 years old 100/33,3%	MG	52	17,33%	30	10%	22	7,33%
	CG	48	16%	24	8%	24	8%
14-18 years old 133/44,3%	MG	68	22,66%	41	13,66%	27	9,0%
	CG	65	21,66%	40	13,33%	25	8,33%
Total 300/100%	MG	145	48,33%	84	28%	61	20,33%
	CG	155	51,66%	86	28,66%	69	23%

If patients have complaints that go beyond the actual dental pathology, as well as therapeutically resistant dysfunctional disorders, a neurological examination of these patients was carried out, which was carried out in the department of rehabilitation of neurological patients of the Bukhara regional hospital.

For clinical and anthropometric assessment of the parameters of the head - determination of the shape of the skull; head circumference, head length, head width, vertical or vertical diameter of the head, the transverse size of the forehead, the size of the base of the head and face parameters were measured by the method of N. Shomirzaev 1998.

The examined were distributed into groups according to the type of occlusion in accordance with the classification of Persina L.S. and ICD-10: with distal occlusion (DO), mesial occlusion (MO), cross occlusion and physiological occlusion (PO). To study the features of occlusal surfaces of teeth and dentitions in adolescents (14-18 years old), 25 adolescents were examined; adolescents with intact dentitions and an orthognathic bite (Engle class I) were selected for CG without functional disorders in the TMJ.

During a dental examination, the patient was followed according to the recommended scheme (3). To identify the elasticity of the articular elements, A. Gegbeg test (1970) was used; TMJ was palpated in two ways directly through the skin and from the external auditory canal. Palpable masticatory muscles, muscles of the neck and girdle of the upper limb. Used sliding and tick-borne techniques. The presence of pain during palpation was an indicator of the presence of trigger points (TP).

The study of occlusion, its relief, the relationship of the dentition of the upper jaw (u / j) and lower jaw (l / j) was carried out by us in statics (central occlusion (CO), central ratio (CR)) and the PO dynamics using the front arc of the OSUNG articulator and STRATOS-300. Casts were obtained with standard metal spoons with alginate material, models were cast from super gypsum. To determine the position of the military unit in relation to the TMJ and oriented towards the Frankfurt horizontal, "The Denar Slidematic face bow technique" methodology was used (S.F. Rosenstiel, M.F. Land, Junhei Fujimoto. 1988); using the front arc, the position of the military unit in the skull space was determined; these data were transferred through the front arc to the articulator. Thus, 50 diagnostic models of 22 boys and 28 girls of young men were studied; occlusal contacts were determined in the position of the central organ, in the front, back, and side occlusions (according to the method of O.Zh. Nazarov 2010); and for a

biometric study of the localization of occlusal contacts of teeth of the military unit u / j, l / j, in individuals with TMJ dysfunction, the occlusiography method was applied (V.Y. Milikevichem, A.P.Kibkalo, L.P.Ivanovim(1984)).

To determine the angles of transversal curves, we additionally drew a horizontal line. It was formed by connecting the same hillocks of the upper first and second molars on the right and left (buccal on the right with buccal on the left or palatine on the right with palatine on the left); that is, the positions of the Spee curve (SPEE) and the Wilson curve were studied.

The data of clinical examinations and the results of additional studies were recorded in specially designed maps, which took into account passport data, medical history, diagnosis, and treatment plan, laboratory diagnostic and functional studies.

In order to study and analyze the medical and social aspects of the course and outcome of the TMJ pathology in adolescents, the neurological status of adolescents with pain syndromes of the dysfunction (PSD) TMJ was evaluated.

Objective examination data were entered into the map “Objective data on examination of TMJ and chewing muscles” and “Verbal Descriptive Pain Assessment Scale” (VDP) was used to score pain sensations (VAL) - VerbalDescriptorScale (1990) and 6 pain response responses were evaluated: from 0 points (no pain); up to 10 points (unbearable pain); and using surface electromyography (EMG), the muscle balance between pairs of symmetrical masticatory muscles was evaluated.

Using the SF-36 quality of life (QOL) scale, the patient studied the level of general well-being and the degree of his satisfaction with those areas of life that affect his well-being. 36 questions are grouped into 8 groups: - physical functioning; - role activity; - bodily pain; - general health; - viability; - social functioning; - emotional state; and - mental health. In addition, the subjective functional status of the individual (MedicalOutcomesStudyShortForm) was measured.

For statistical processing, the obtained data calculated the group arithmetic mean (M) and standard error of the mean (m), which are presented in the final tables and using the Statisticaver program. 7.0 The differences were considered significant at P <0.05.

The results of the study and their discussion. According to the results of anthropometric parameters of the face and DVA in children and adolescents with TMJ pathologies, healthy children and young people aged 6–9, 10–13, and 14–18 years old showed that the physiological height of the face (PHF) in 6–9-year-old healthy boys average 16.9 ± 0.11 sm (growth rate 1.6%), and for girls this parameter varied on average 17.1 ± 0.14 * sm (growth rate 2.2%). The morphological height of the face (MHF) for boys of this group is on average 11.8 ± 0.60 (growth rate of 1.7%), and for girls on average 11.4 ± 0.42 cm (growth rate of 1.1%).

PHF in 6–9 year old male children with TMJ pathologies is on average 16.4 ± 0.09 (growth rate 0.6%), and on average 17.4 ± 0.03 * cm in girls (growth rate 2.2%). In 6–9-year-old boys and youths with TMJ pathologies, the morphological height of the face varied on average equal to 11.0 ± 0.04 (growth rate 0.6%), and in girls it was on average 11.6 ± 0.08 * (growth rate 4 , 6%).

Studies have shown that PHF in 10-13 year old healthy boys fluctuated, on average, 17.4 ± 0.09 cm (growth rate is absent), and in girls this parameter, on average, 17.4 ± 0.12 * cm (growth rate -2.0%). MHF for healthy boys fluctuated on average equal to 12.2 ± 0.03 (growth rate - 1.2%), and for girls on average 11.8 ± 0.62 (growth rate - 1.4%). In 10-13 year old male children with TMJ pathologies, PHF ranged on average 16.8 ± 0.10 (growth rate - 0.6%), and in girls on average 17.0 ± 0.05 cm (growth rate equal to 1 , 2%). MHF in 10-13 year old boys of this group fluctuated on average equal to 11.8 ± 0.01 cm (growth rate - 2.4%), while in girls it was within the average of 11.9 ± 0.12 * cm (pace growth is equal - 1.8%), (table №. 2).

Table № 2.

Morphometric parameters in children and youth with pathological TMJ and healthy group

Age and gender	6-9 years old; n= 67		10-13 years old; n= 100		14-18 years old; n= 133	
	Boys n= 30	Girls n= 37	Boys n= 48	Girls n= 52	Boys n= 52	Girls n= 81
Face parameters (sm)						

Physio height	face	CG	16,9±0,11	17,1±0,14*	17,4±0,09	17,4±0,12*	19,0±0,20	19,0±0,04*
		MG	16,4±0,09	17,4±0,03*	16,8±0,10	17,5±0,08*	19,1±0,02	18,8±0,02*
Morpho height	face	CG	11,8±0,60	11,4±0,42	12,2±0,03	11,8±0,62	13,0±0,02	13,0±0,40
		MG	11,0±0,04	11,6±0,08*	11,8±0,01	11,9±0,12*	12,2±0,42	12,0±0,60*
Height ver. parts of the face		CG	5,9±0,06	5,8±0,25	6,2±0,34	6,0±0,45	6,9±0,28	6,6±0,38
		MG	5,6±0,06	5,9±0,04	5,7±0,06	6,0±0,01	6,4±0,09	6,8±0,48
Medium Height parts of the face		CG	5,9±0,05	5,9±0,02*	6,2±0,05	6,4±0,08*	6,4±0,12	6,9±0,02*
		MG	5,5±0,02	5,9±0,02*	5,9±0,08	6,4±0,06*	6,0±0,02	6,9±0,01*
Height lower parts of the face		CG	5,8±0,08	5,9±0,02*	5,9±0,01	6,4±0,08*	6,2±0,01	6,9±0,07*
		MG	5,7±0,08	5,6±0,02	6,4±0,06	5,6±0,02	6,5±0,06	5,8±0,07
Fibonacci number		CG	1:1,622	1:1,55	1:1,624	1:1,90	1:1,980	1:1,90
		MG	1:1,534	1:1,668	1:1,581	1:1,60	1:1,60	1:1,45

Note: * - confidence indicator (P <0.05) compared with the previous age.

The highest growth rate of PHF in healthy male children is observed at 14-18 years old, and the lowest - at 6-9 years. In healthy girls, the highest rate is also observed in boys at 6-9 years old and 14-18 years old (4.2%, 5.2%), and the lowest at 10-13 years (1.1%).

The highest growth rate of PHF in male children with TMJ pathologies is observed at 14-18 years old, and the lowest at the age of 6-9 years. In girls of this group, the highest rate is also noted at 14-18 years old, and the lowest at 6-9 years.

Based on the results of studying the CG examination of the CG, the clinical signs of the absence of functional disorders in the TMJ were identified, which are indicated by the methodological recommendations (3). At the same time, as a result of the study, the complaints of the patients with MG were found to have complaints and common symptoms characteristic of this pathology; i.e; Complaints directly related to TMJ: pain, sound effects (clicks, crunching, crackling), restriction of opening the mouth, uneven displacement and dislocation of the heads of the u / j, blocking the joint, deviation of the l / j to the sides when opening the mouth. (3);

IV. Discussion

Features of occlusal surfaces (OS) of teeth in individuals of MG on the OS of the first and second molars / h also occur at the closure area, however, the number of teeth on the chewing side was greater than on the teeth of the opposite side. In contrast to the CG, the percentage of the absence of sites on the top of the distal palatal hillock increased on the one hand on the second molar. On the OS of the first upper premolar, the erasure site was located on the medial-occlusal slope of the palatine and buccal tubercles. The upper fangs in this group also had their own characteristics. Along with the contact pads of closure on the medial and distal ridges, one-sided abrasion of the top of the tearing hillock to the right or left with a different area was noted. The areas of erasure were localized on the medial slope of the tuber of the upper canine.

The occlusal morphology of the lower first and second premolars and molars, along with the contact points, has erasure areas that are enlarged contact areas of the closure. For fangs l / j in this group, asymmetric contact areas were characteristic in the region of tearing tubercles on the right and left. The areas of erasure that originated from the middle of the tearing tubercle of the canine also went in the asymmetric direction. The contacting areas of the abutment and the areas of erasure on the cutters l / j had the same localization - along the cutting edge with the disappearance of its pattern. Data of intraoral and instrumental analysis of functional occlusion of the exhaust gas in the central nervous system repeats the data of the models; for example, in 3 patients in anterior occlusion there was contact on only one central incisor of the military u / j, as a result of which the l / j when moving forward was shifted to the side until reaching the occlusal contact on the opposite side; in 7 patients, lateral occlusion revealed occlusal contacts on the balancing side.

It should be noted that in all cases, hyperbalancing supercontacts were detected only when analyzing the PO in the articulator, and in OC lateral movements of l / j, at which these contacts appeared, were not detected due to the limitation of the jaw excursion. This is probably due to the fact that when the patient closed his mouth, he developed the usual movement to the forced rear contact position in order to exclude premature contact.

Eccentric occlusal disorders were detected: in 3 patients in the front occlusion supercontacts were established in the chewing groups of teeth, including in 1 patient premature contacts on the molars did not allow the front teeth to close in u / j and l / j. In 3 patients there was no symmetrical contact of the incisors. In total, in all 25 patients, a lateral displacement of the center point relative to the line of the central ratio was established.

When determining the angles of transversal occlusion curves, certain angles were drawn between a horizontally formed joint of the same named tubercles of opposite molars and transversal curves for these teeth separately on the right and left: In the region of the first molars, in all cases they were from 0 to 5.5°. The angles of transversal curves in the region of the second molars in 4 cases ranged from 0 to 5°, in 9 cases to the right and left were from 4.5 to 9.0°, in 4 cases were from 9 and higher degrees: The angles of transversal occlusion curves in the main group in the region of the molars of teeth on the right and left in 2 cases ranged from 0 to 4.5°, in 5 cases ranged from 5,0 to 9.0°, in 12 cases ranged from 9 and above degrees. The angles of transversal curves in the region of second molars in 100% of cases ranged from 9 and above degrees.

Figure № 1. Results of biometric measurements of transversal occlusion curves.

As a result of a semi-professional clinical examination by specialists (neurologists, dentists), objectification of dysfunctional muscle disorders, a clinical diagnosis of the study group of 48 patients from 14-18 years old young men who complained of PSD TMJ was performed.

Depending on the severity of the complaints presented, recorded when using the SCL-90-R scale, patients were divided into two groups (table № 3). Moreover, to assess clinically significant complaints, the “Symptomatic Index” of the SCL-90-R (PST) scale was taken into account, which has a normalized indicator in the range of up to 22.6 ± 1.44 points for the total of affirmative answers. Group I consisted of patients whose PST index exceeded 24 points, and group 1 consisted of patients whose PST index was less than 24 points.

In turn, the 1st group of patients was divided into two subgroups (“A” and “B”), differing in the representation in each of them of functional disorders of the TMJ chewing muscles, data on which were obtained using the “Clinical Index of TMJ Dysfunction” scale [Helkimo M., 1976]. Subgroup “A” consisted of patients with Helkimo index over 5 points, and group “B” - with Helkimo index up to 5 points.

Table №3.

Clinical groups of examined patients, depending on complaints

Patient groups	ICD-10	Col. Patients and group encoding

Group I (symptomatic PST index - over 24)	subgroup "A" (Helkimo index - 5-20)	K07.6	F 45.3 F 45.4 F 45.8	n = 18 K-F
	"B" (Helkimo index - up to 5)	K07.6	F 45.3 F 45.4 F 45.8	n = 18 O-F
Group II (symptomatic PST index - up to 24)		K07.6 dysfunction index Helkimo - 5-20	F 45.3 F 45.4 F 45.8	n = 12 K-0

As can be seen, the clinical group 1 included patients with a high representation of somatic complaints. Subgroup A included patients (18 patients; 37.5%), whose clinical and psychopathological examination and analysis of the disease made it possible to attribute their complaints to those characteristic of mixed manifestations of the disease, namely, neurological disorders with a prevailing muscular-tonic and functional disorders of the masticatory muscles (ICD-10: K07.6), combined with somatoform disorders (ICD-10: F45.0), manifested in the form of psycho-vegetative disorders (ICD-10: F45.3); chronic somatoform pain disorder (ICD-10: F45.4); psycho-vegetative disorders with severe dysfunction of other organs and systems, including “grinding of teeth” (ICD-10: F45.8). Subgroup “B” included patients (18 patients; 37.5%), whose clinical and psychopathological examination and analysis of the disease made it possible to attribute their complaints to those characteristic of somatoform disorders, which are classified by MKB-10 to F45.3, F45.4 and 45.8, but differing in the absence of neurological disorders proper, namely: pronounced muscle-tonic and functional disorders of the masticatory muscles (according to ICD-10: K07.6).

The clinical group II consisted of patients (12 patients; 25%), the clinical features of the disease of which were characterized by pronounced neurological symptom complexes, namely, muscular-tonic and functional disorders of the masticatory muscles (according to ICD-10: K07.6). At the same time, the result of their clinical and psychopathological examination and analysis of the disease allowed them to reject the presence of any somatoform symptomatic manifestations.

The main clinical complaint in the examined patients with PSD TMJ was pain; including in the area of l / j of the joint and chewing muscles. In addition to the actual pains, the following painful sensations were the following: limitation of mobility of the u / l, crunching and clicking in the TMJ, discomfort in the TMJ and the lateral surfaces of the face, fatigue of the masticatory muscles during conversation and during meals.

In general, this general nature of the complaints required differential diagnosis and differentiation of the diagnosis of PSD from TMJ from TMJ arthropathy, trigeminal neuralgia and other types of chronic facial pain, as well as osteochondrosis of the cervical spine and other diseases of the head and neck, accompanied by pain and impaired movement.

During a clinical examination of patients, localization areas were identified, which were indicated by the studied patients: upper part of the face; TMJ area; facial muscles and chewing muscles; face area.

Pain in the upper part of the face: It turned out that the complaints of patients whose pain was localized in the face region differed in the nature of their prevalence. At the time of the examination, 7 people (14.58%) complained of unilateral diffuse pain in the upper half of the face without clear localization. The average intensity on the VDP pain scale was 3.8 ± 0.9 points. Of these, unilateral pain with irradiation worried 3 people (6.25%). The average intensity on the VDP pain scale turned out to be 4.2 ± 1.1 points. It should be noted that this symptom bothered patients during clinical diagnosis, they mainly complained of a somatoform nature (group 1).

Complaints of severity and pain in the neck region were noted in 10 patients (20.84%) with pain in the face and the presence of a concomitant spinal disease in the form of osteochondrosis of the cervical spine in a short history. The average intensity on the VDP pain scale in them turned out to be 2.4 ± 2.5 points. In a short-term history of local daily pain in the upper part of the face, 12 people (25%) noted, with less than half of them (10.4%) indicating a one-sided nature of the pain without clear localization.

25 patients (52%) had a short-term history of pain on both sides in the projection m. temporalis (pain in the temple); 4 patients (8.3%) had local pain in the forehead. The average intensity on the VDP pain scale was 4.5 ± 1.2

points. These types of pain were characteristic of most patients with pain dysfunction syndrome (subgroup "A" of group I, as well as group II).

Complaints of a burning sensation in the face region were noted by 2 people (4.2%), and 5 patients (10.4%) with traumatic damage to the branches of n presented unpleasant sensations in the form of local numbness and decreased sensitivity of the facial skin. Trigeminus. The average intensity of burning sensation as a variant of pain sensation on the VDP scale turned out to be 3.5 ± 0.5 points. For a group of patients with PSD, TMJ was characterized by complaints of burning sensation in the oral cavity at the time of examination and in a short history. At the same time, the aggregate assessment of complaints of pains with different characteristics in the upper part of the face using the Hotelling's Trace method did not reveal differences in the groups and subgroups of the subjects ($p = 0.482$).

The results of a multivariate analysis of variance, showing the degree of significance of a factor, demonstrate that the complaints made by patients about a certain type of pain in the face area also cannot be an important clinical sign, which serves as a distinguishing characteristic of the clinical groups and subgroups identified in this study ($p = 0, 2 - 0.7$) (Figure № 2).

Fig. Clinical symptomatology of the orofacial region (average number of positive responses in groups)

As you can see, the representation of individual complaints in groups and subgroups varied in frequency. So, complaints of pain in the face were found with the same frequency in patients of subgroup A and B of group 1, while patients of group II rarely noted local pain in the face and shoulder pain. At the same time, almost every patient of group 2 noted a pain in the face, which was, rather, an undifferentiated one.

V. Conclusion

Thus, comprehensive approaches to diagnosis in children and adolescents with TMJ pathologies, including morphological and clinical studies, including analysis of functional occlusion, as well as the study of medical, social and neurological factors, are an important link in determining the interdependence of the formation of pathological symptoms of TMJ, occlusal and neuromuscular disorders.

The study showed that MHF and PHF in children and young people with TMJ pathologies increase in multidirectional indicators (especially noticeably in 14-18 years old) than in healthy children. The growth rate of the anthropometric parameters of the face in healthy children is almost the same at regular intervals, and in children with TMJ pathologies they change spasmodically.

Asymmetric localization of the "areas of abrasion" of the occlusal surfaces of the teeth of the same name is one of the main criteria for functional occlusion disorders contributing to the occurrence of TMJ dysfunction, while

it can be said that TMJ dysfunctions are directly dependent on the values of the angles of transversal occlusion curves.

VI.References:

1. Ashnokova, I.A. Electromyographic diagnosis of masticatory muscles in patients with temporomandibular joint dysfunction syndrome / I.A. Ashnokova, Yu.V. Kotsyubinskaya // Biopsychosocial approach to the problem of neurorehabilitation: Mater. Vseros. scientific and practical. conf. (05/23/2015). - SPb. : Man and his health, 2015. – p. 8.
2. Badanin, V.V. Diagnosis of functional disorders of the temporomandibular joint using computed and magnetic resonance imaging and their orthopedic treatment [Text] / V.V. Badanin // Institute of Dentistry. - 2000. - No. 1. - p. 34–36.
3. Gafforov S.A. Nazarov O.J. "Syndromes and symptoms of the temporomandibular joint. Clinic, diagnosis and treatment." Method. recommendations. Tashkent-2012.31 p.
4. Gafforov S.A. Abdirimov I.S. "Medical deontology and psychiatry in dental practice" Method. Recommendations Tashkent 2014. 46 p.
5. Dolgaev A.A. Comprehensive diagnosis of occlusal disorders of the dentition in patients with pathology of the temporomandibular joint // Bulletin of new medical technologies. 2008. No. 2.- p.80.
6. Egorov P.M., Karapetyan I.S. Pain dysfunction of the temporomandibular joint. M, Publishing House Medicine, 2006.-122p.
7. Iordanishvili, A.K. et al. Comprehensive treatment of diseases of the temporomandibular joint in people of older age groups [Text] / A.K. Iordanishvili et al. // Institute of Dentistry. - 2012. - No. 1. - P.76–78.
8. Iordanishvili, A.K., Serikov, A.A., Polens, A.A. On the treatment of diseases of the temporomandibular joint by orthopedic dentists in outpatient facilities of various ownership [Text] / A.K. Iordanishvili, A.A. Serikov, A.A. Polens // Institute of Dentistry. - 2011. - No. 3. - p.10-12.
9. Dentistry. Guide Tashkent-2018. 875 s Under the leadership of Professor S. A. Gafforov.
10. Sysolyatin P.G., Ilyin A.A., Dergilev A.P. Classification of diseases and injuries of the temporomandibular joint // M: medical book.; N. Novgorod: Publishing house of the NGMA 2001.-76 p.
11. Khvatova V.A. Functional occlusion is normal and pathological. - M.: Medicine, 2003. –p. 27-30.
12. Gaffarov S.A., Saidov A.A. The importance of matrix metalloproteases in the pathology of the temporomandibular joint in children // International Journal on Integrated Education, Volume-03, Issue-V may 2020. 65-68.
13. Daniel, R. Stress-Related Adaptive Versus Maladaptive Coping and Temporomandibular Disorder Pain / R. Daniel, T. John Mike, O. Schierz // J. Orofac. Pain. – 2012. – Vol. 26, N 3. – P. 181–190.
14. Greene, C.S. Concepts of TMD etiology : Effects on diagnosis and treatment // Temporomandibular disorders : an evidence-based approach to diagnosis and treatment / D.M. Laskin, C.S. Greene, W.L. Hylander. – Chicago: Quintessence 170 Publishing Co., 2006. – P. 219–228.
15. Cakir!Ozkan N., Sarikaya B., Erkorkmaz U. et al Static Approaches to Orofacial Pain and Temporomandibular disorders, 2014.-84.
16. Olimov S.Sh., Saidov A.A., Gaffarov S.A., Akmalaliev N.N. Assessment of hepatobiliary system with dentoalveolar anomalies in school children //International journal of Research (IJR), Volume-06, Issue-03 march 2019. 576-583.
17. Olimov S.Sh., Gaffarov S.A., Yakubov R.K., Saidov A.A., Badriddinov B.B Prevalence of dentoalveolar anomalies in 6-16 years children according to retrospective data analysis //International journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation, Volume-24, Issue-09 2020. ISSN:1475-7192.
18. Saidov A.A. Assessment of some indicators of oral liquid in children with the pathology of the temporomandibular joint // Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research, Volume-09, Issue-01 January 2020. 59-63.
19. Tvrđy, P. Methods of imaging in the diagnosis of temporomandibular joint disorders / P. Tvrđy // Biomedical papers of the Medical Faculty of the University Palacky, Olomouc, Czechoslovakia. – 2007. – Vol. 151, № 1. – P. 133-136.
20. Wang, M. Q. The effect of physiological nonbalanced occlusion on the thickness of the temporomandibular joint disc: a pilot autopsy study / M. Q. Wang, J. J. He, G. Li // Journal of Prosthetic Dentistry. – 2008. – Vol. 99, № 2. – P. 148-152.

21. Wassell, R. W. The treatment of temporomandibular disorders withstabilizing splints in general dental practice: One-year follow-up / R. W. Wassell, N.Adams, P. J. Kelly // Journal Of The American Dental Association. – 2006. – Vol. 8, №137. – P. 1089-1098.